

Alkylidene-(arylidene) Succinic Acids and Anhydrides

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Manuscript received 15 February 1978, accepted 7 July 1978

Alkylidene-(arylidene) succinic acids (1a & 1b) yielded corresponding anhydrides (2a & 2b) with acetyl chloride. Diacid (1b) gave 2-isobutylidene-3-carboxy-3,4-dehydrotetralone-1(3b) on treatment with conc. H_2SO_4 or PPA, and (1a) yielded 2-cyclohexylidene-3-carboxy-3,4-dehydrotetralone-1(3a) with conc. H_2SO_4 .

FULGIDES are of interest for photochromic properties¹. Highly conjugated anhydrides (2a) and (2b) were synthesised. The Stobbe condensation of alkylidenesuccinates and benzaldehyde gave the alkylidenepheryl itaconate which on saponification yielded the corresponding diacids (1a) and (1b). The same diacids (1a) and (1b) were also obtained by Stobbe condensation of phenyl itaconates with cyclohexanone and ethyl methyl ketone followed by saponification of the acid-esters.

The diacids on treatment with acetyl chloride yielded the corresponding anhydrides (2a): m.p. 90-92°, IR 1815 (anhydride C=O) and 1232 cm^{-1} (C-O-C)², PMR ($CDCl_3$): δ 1.41-1.87 (m, 8H, 5 axial & 3 equatorial protons), 2.99-3.11 (m, 2H, deshielded equatorial alicyclic protons near double bond), 7.38 (s, 5H, Ar-H), 7.59 (s, 1H, -CH=) and (2b) which did not crystallise and was identified by TLC and its hydrolysis to the diacid (1b). However, these anhydrides were nonphotochromic. Friedel-Crafts cyclization of the anhydrides with anhydrous $AlCl_3$ yielded only diacids (1a) and (1b).

Cyclization of 1,1-cyclohexylidene-3-phenylprop-2-ene-1, 2-dicarboxylic acid (1a) with conc. H_2SO_4 at room temperature for 24 hours gave a product, m.p. 220-22° to which was given the structure 2-cyclohexylidene-3-carboxy-3, 4-dehydrotetralone-1 (3a) on the basis of analytical and spectral evidences: UV λ_{max} 245(4.62), 294-96(3.80), 300-305 (infl.), 340-45 (infl.), 350 nm (3.71); IR 1710 (α, β -unsaturated acid), 1690 cm^{-1} (aryl ketone); PMR (DMSO-D6): δ 1.77-2.56 (m, 10H, alicyclic), 7.52-8.49 (m, 4H, Ar-H), 8.09 (s, 1H, -CH=), 10.12 (s, 1H, -COOH). High resolution PMR spectrum of the product (3a) depicted the aromatic multiplet pattern for the 1,2-substituted benzene system which distinctly showed that cyclization occurred in the aromatic ring. The lowest field situated aromatic proton was HA (due to nearby carbonyl) which appears at 8.39-8.49 δ with $J_{AB}=7.5$ Hz and $J_{AC}=2.5$ Hz³; HD appears at slightly higher field (8.10-8.20 δ)

with $J_{DC}=8$ Hz and $J_{DB}=2.5$ Hz³; HC and HB protons appear as a symmetrical multiplet with a complex pattern at higher field (7.52-7.79 δ).

1-Phenyl-4-methylhexa-1,3-diene-2, 3-dicarboxylic acid (1b) on similar treatment with conc. H_2SO_4 gave the product with very similar spectral properties and was assigned the structure 2-isobutylidene-3-carboxy-3, 4-dehydrotetralone-1(3b).

Cyclization of the diacid (1b) with PPA at 100° for one hour yielded the same product 2-isobutylidene-3-carboxy-3,4-dehydrotetralone-1(3b).

An alternative structure for the cyclized products could be envisaged as indenones (4a) and (4b) as was obtained from 1-aryl-4, 4-diphenylbutadiene-2,3-dicarboxylic acid anhydride⁴. However, since the materials were not coloured and UV spectra very dissimilar from compounds having indenone structures⁵, the tetralone structures (3a) and (3b) were preferred. Further, the system (1) having an E-s-trans structure would preferably cyclize to tetralone rather than indenone, as in the latter case -COOH group is trans to the Ph group. Further, the facile cyclisation occurring with the acids and not the anhydride supports the tetralone structure.

a : $R^1 R^2 = \text{Cyclo } C_6H_{10}$
b : $R^1 R^2 = \text{Me, Et}$.

Experimental

*1,1-Cyclohexylidene-3-phenylprop-2-ene-1,2-dicarboxylic acid (1a)*⁶—1,1-Cyclohexylidene-2-carbomethoxy-3-phenylprop-2-ene-1-carboxylic acid on saponification with 8% alc. KOH solution gave (1a) in quantitative yield which crystallised from ethanol-water, m.p. 213-14° (Found: C, 71.50, H, 6.38; equiv. wt 145.5. $C_{17}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 71.31; H, 6.33%, equiv. wt 143.1); UV (EtOH): 258 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.10); IR (nujol): 1675 (α , β -unsaturated acid), 1633, 1598 (exocyclic and ethylenic double bonds) and 1272 cm^{-1} (C-O stretch).

1-Phenyl-4-methylhexa-1, 3-diene-2, 3-dicarboxylic acid (1b)—A mixture of dimethylsuccinate (7.3 g) and ethyl methyl ketone (3.6 g) was added to potassium tert. butoxide (2.0 g potassium, 50 ml tert butanol) at room temperature. After 30 minutes, working up of the Stobbe product yielded 2-carbomethoxy-3-methylpent-2-ene-1-carboxylic acid (8.0 g) as viscous brown oil, crystallized from ether-petroleum ether (60-80°) as rosette of needles, m.p. 60-70° (Found: equiv. wt 188.1, $C_9H_{14}O_4$ requires equiv. wt 162). The corresponding diester, 1, 2-dicarbomethoxy-3-methylpent-2-ene was obtained in quantitative yield by esterification with diazomethane. Stobbe condensation of this diester (3.2 g) and benzaldehyde (2.0 g) at room temperature in potassium tert. butoxide (0.7 g potassium in 20 ml *t*-butanol), under anhydrous conditions for 1 hour yielded 1-phenyl-3-carbomethoxy-4-methylhexa-1, 3-diene-2-oic acid (3.7 g) as brown oil which on saponification with 8% alc. KOH yielded the diacid (1b), crystallized from ethanol-water, m.p. 215 (Found: C, 68.98, H, 6.12, equiv. wt. 130.5. $C_{15}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 69.21; H, 6.20%; equiv. wt. 130.1); UV (EtOH): 262 nm (ϵ 4.07); IR: 1693, 1633, 1610, 1277 cm^{-1} .

1,1-Cyclohexylidene-3-phenylprop-2-ene-1, 2-dicarboxylic acid anhydride (2a)—The diacid (1a) (1.0 g) was refluxed with acetyl chloride (10 ml) for 2 hr on a water-bath, excess acetyl chloride removed under reduced pressure and the residue crystallized from benzene-hexane to give colourless crystals of (2a) (0.8 g), m.p. 90-2° (Found: C, 76.08; H, 5.91. $C_{17}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 76.12; H, 5.97%); IR: 1815, 1232 cm^{-1} ; NMR ($CDCl_3$): δ 1.41-1.87, 2.99-3.11, 7.38, 7.59.

1-Phenyl-4-methylhexa-1, 3-diene-2, 3-dicarboxylic acid anhydride (2b)—Similarly (1b) gave the anhydride (2b) in quantitative yield which did not crystallize.

2-Cyclohexylidene-3-carboxy-3,4-dehydrotetralone-1 (3a)—

Diacid (1a) (1.0 g) was treated with conc. H_2SO_4 (5 ml) for 24 hr at room temperature and then

pouring of the reaction mixture into crushed ice yielded the monoacid 3a (0.9 g), crystallized from ether-petroleum ether (60-80°), m.p. 220-22° (Found: C, 76.14; H, 5.92, equiv. wt. 269.1. $C_{17}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 76.12; H, 5.97%; equiv. wt. 268.3); UV (EtOH): 245, 294-96, 350 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.62, 3.80, and 3.71), 300-5 & 340-45 (infl.) IR (Nujol) 1710, 1690 cm^{-1} ; NMR (DMSO- D_6): δ 1.77-2.56, 7.52-8.49, 8.09, 10.12.

2-Isobutylidene-3-carboxy-3, 4-dehydrotetralone-1 (3b)—Diacid (1b) (1.0 g) on similar treatment with conc. H_2SO_4 yielded (3b) (0.9 g), crystallized from ether-petroleum ether (60-80°), m. p. 184-5° (Found: C, 74.31; H, 5.81; equiv. wt. 240.2. $C_{15}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 74.38; H, 5.79%; equiv. wt. 242.2); UV (EtOH): 245, 293-95, 349 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.62, 3.58 and 3.65), 300-6 and 340-45 (infl.); IR (nujol): 1715, 1688 cm^{-1} ; NMR ($CDCl_3$): δ 0.74 (t, 3H, Me of Et.), 1.84 (s, 3H, Me), 2.26 (q, 2H, $-CH_2-$ of Et.), 7.48-8.22 (m, 4H, Ar-H), 8.08 (s, 1H, $-CH=$), 7.79 (s, 1H, $-COOH$).

Diacid (1b) (1.0 g) on treatment with PPA (generated on water bath from 6-7 g phosphorous pentoxide and 5-6 ml orthophosphoric acid under anhydrous conditions) at 100° for 1 hr and on pouring the reaction mixture into crushed ice yielded (3b) (0.8 g) identified by its m.p., m.m.p. with authentic sample; analytical and spectral data.

Acknowledgement

One of us (SB) is thankful to the Nagpur University and U.G.C. for a fellowship.

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